

PHYSICS

CALCULATION OF THERMAL EXPANSION COEFFICIENT AND THE DIFFERENCE OF HEAT CAPACITIES OF A BINARY MIXTURE CONSISTING OF N-FETTY ALDEHYDE - ISO FETTY ALDEHYDE IN A RANGE OF STATE PARAMETERS AND IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Thermal expansion coefficient and the difference of unknown values related mixtures consisting of N-Fetty Aldehyde and some other parameters.

Keywords: N-Fetty Aldehyde, Thermal expansion, Binary mixtures.

We are hydrostatically hydrostatic of normal oil (N-oil), - iso-fatty aldehydes and their binary mixtures (N-fatty aldehyde 80%-iso-fatty aldehyde 20% and N-fatty aldehyde 88%-iso-fatty aldehyde 12%) we performed cycles [1-3]. In order to take advantage of the obtained usage, a binary mixture three-state equation was written with the help of the machine used [4-6]. This provides more benefits for a wider area of use and heat capacities. The binary system equation of state named above

$$P = A(T) \cdot \rho^2 + B(T)\rho^2 \quad (1)$$

Here: P- pressure (Mpa) ρ - density (g/cm²), and A(T) and B(T) are coefficients depending on temperature. Where

$$A(T) = \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i \left(\frac{T}{100}\right) \quad B(T) = \sum_{i=1}^n b_i \left(\frac{T}{100}\right)^i \quad (2)$$

Here, a_i and b_i have a certain fixed quantity for the liquid of each shallowness. The values of a_i and b_i for the system consisting of N-fatty aldehyde - isofatty aldehyde are given in table 1.

As a result of the inspections, it was found that the difference between the calculated numerical value of the thermal expansion coefficient of the taken system and the experimental value is within an error of 0.10-0.2%.

Table 1.

Coefficients	Material			
	N-fatty aldehyde	Iso Fatty aldehyde	88%N-fatty aldehyde +12% iso-fatty aldehyde	80% N-fatty aldehyde +12% iso fat aldehydes
a_0	$-1,18483 \cdot 10^3$	$1,50491 \cdot 10^3$	$-1,19752 \cdot 10^3$	$-1,26047 \cdot 10^3$
a_1	$5,48072 \cdot 10^0$	$8,28215 \cdot 10^0$	$5,62546 \cdot 10^0$	$6,15025 \cdot 10^0$
a_2	$-9,67988 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-1,70878 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1,00987 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1,14729 \cdot 10^{-2}$
a_3	$6,68800 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1,30740 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7,07900 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8,25000 \cdot 10^{-6}$
b_0	$1,63939 \cdot 10^3$	$4,36078 \cdot 10^3$	$1,82408 \cdot 10^3$	$2,12788 \cdot 10^3$
b_1	$-7,98725 \cdot 10^0$	$-2,92775 \cdot 10^1$	$-9,08732 \cdot 10^0$	$-1,15281 \cdot 10^1$
b_2	$2,05610 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7,73247 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2,38123 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3,02997 \cdot 10^{-2}$
b_3	$9,92000 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-6,08520 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-1,32280 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1,89300 \cdot 10^{-5}$

From the generalized equation of state to calculate the coefficient of thermal expansion and the difference in heat capacities of the system consisting of n-fatty and isofatty aldehydes at different concentrations

$$p = \left[\sum_{i=0}^2 k_i T_n^i \sum_{i=0}^3 C_i \left(\frac{T}{T_n}\right)^i \right] \rho^2 + \left[\sum_{i=0}^2 l_i T_n^i \sum_{i=0}^3 d_i \left(\frac{T}{T_n}\right)^i \right] \rho^3 \quad (3)$$

Here T_n system, T_{n1} and T_{n2} – the normal boiling temperature of the first and second component, respectively, and

$$T_n = T_{n1}(1 - x) + T_{n2}x$$

x is the amount of relative mass of the second component; that c_i , l_i , d_i are the constants of binary mixtures consisting of N-fatty-isofatty aldehydes and their values are given in table 2 and table 3.

(3) – the value of the coefficients c_i and d_i of the equation.

Table 2.

Coefficients	Binary system	
	N-fatty and isofatty aldehyde	
c ₀	5,063559	
c ₁	-12,169629	
c ₂	11,108113	
c ₃	-3,012612	
d ₀	8,825187	
d ₁	-16,139685	
d ₂	11,249855	
d ₃	-2,940055	

(3) the value of the coefficients k_i and l_i, of Eq.

Table 3

Coefficients	Binary system	
	N-fatty and isofatty aldehyde	
k ₀	6,49206 · 10 ²	
k ₁	-3,16236 · 10 ⁰	
k ₂	2,32271 · 10 ⁻³	
l ₀	-1,20081 · 10 ⁵	
l ₁	7,10283 · 10 ²	
l ₂	-1,041181 · 10 ⁰	

Equation (1) is used for the isothermal expansion coefficient and heat capacity difference of the studied binary system. What we know from thermodynamics

$$\alpha_p = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right)_p; \beta_T = \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial P} \right)_T; C_p - C_v = \frac{\alpha_p^2 T}{\beta_T \rho} \quad (4)$$

If we consider formulas (1) and (3) in the formula, then

$$\alpha_p = -\frac{A'(T)+B'(T)\cdot\rho^6}{2A(T)+8B(T)\cdot\rho^6}; \beta_T = \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial P} \right)_T = \frac{1}{2\cdot A(T)\rho^2+8B(T)\rho^8}$$

With the help of formulas (4) and (5), it is possible to calculate βT values of α_p and (C_p - C_v) in a wide range of temperature and pressure and at different concentrations. These values are given in table 4.

Thermal expansion coefficient of normal fatty aldehyde ($\alpha \cdot 10^3, K^{-1}$)

Table 4.

P, MP _a T, k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	1,2892	1,2411	1,1968	1,1199	1,055	1,0001	0,9522	0,9101	0,8729	0,8397	0,8098	0,7828
320	1,4797	1,4193	1,3646	1,2722	1,1966	1,1334	1,0796	1,0332	0,9826	0,9568	0,9249	0,8863
340	1,6235	1,5533	1,4862	1,3760	1,2888	1,2177	1,1584	1,1081	1,0647	1,0269	0,9936	0,9639
360		1,6504	1,5679	1,4373	1,3377	1,2688	1,1944	1,1407	1,095	1,0557	1,0214	0,9911
380		1,7254	1,6233	1,4683	1,3551	1,268	1,1986	1,1417	1,0941	1,0536	1,0185	0,9879
400		1,7991	1,6704	1,4843	1,3549	1,2586	1,1837	1,1235	1,074	1,0319	0,9961	0,9651
420		1,8983	1,7303	1,502	1,3516	1,2438	1,1620	1,0974	1,045	1,0043	0,9644	0,9326
440		2,0615	1,8304	1,5393	1,3597	1,2359	1,1445	1,0738	1,0172	0,9707	0,9317	0,8885
460		2,3501	2,0076	1,6168	1,3937	1,2467	1,1413	1,0615	0,9986	0,9475	0,9051	0,8692
480		2,8865	2,3227	1,7612	1,4705	1,2885	1,1622	1,0687	0,9962	0,9381	0,8904	0,8504
500		3,9632	2,8899	2,0131	1,6124	1,3764	1,2185	1,1044	1,0175	0,9489	0,8931	0,8463
Thermal expansion coefficient of iso fatty aldehyde ($\alpha \cdot 10^3, K^{-1}$)												
300	1,4198	1,3573	1,3011	1,2062	1,1201	1,0649	1,0104	0,9635	0,9226	0,8865	0,8545	0,8258
320	1,6014	1,5223	1,4530	1,3397	1,2506	1,1782	1,1182	1,0672	1,0235	0,9854	0,9518	0,9226
340	1,7416	1,6414	1,5562	1,4222	1,3206	1,2405	1,1753	1,1211	1,0752	1,0357	1,0013	0,9709
360	1,8550	1,7266	1,6218	1,4637	1,3491	1,2613	1,1917	1,1347	1,0872	1,0468	1,0119	0,9815
380	1,3663	1,7981	1,6674	1,4801	1,3507	1,2549	1,1807	1,1211	1,0720	1,0308	0,9956	0,9652
400	2,1117	1,8820	1,7146	1,4888	1,3413	1,2358	1,1561	1,0933	1,0424	1,0000	0,9643	0,9335
420	2,3469	2,0121	1,7882	1,6078	1,3356	1,2172	1,1300	1,0627	0,0087	0,9645	0,3275	0,8959
440	2,7828	2,2414	1,9215	1,5568	1,3487	1,2117	1,1134	1,0389	0,9803	0,9328	0,8932	0,8598
460	3,6974	2,6643	2,1633	1,6591	1,3961	1,2309	1,1159	1,0307	0,9645	0,9115	0,8678	0,8312
480	6,1678	3,4889	2,5994	1,8474	1,4968	1,2883	1,1479	1,0462	0,9685	0,9070	0,8569	0,8153
500	226381	5,2483	3,3905	2,1701	1,6758	1,3989	1,2209	1,0943	0,9994	0,9253	0,8656	0,8163

75% normal fatty aldehyde + 25% isofatty aldehyde heat index
($\alpha \cdot 10^3, K^{-1}$)

P,MP _a T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	1,3213	1,2698	1,2225	1,1412	1,0733	0,0157	0,9661	0,9227	0,8845	0,1505	0,8201	0,7925
320	1,5098	1,4448	1,3866	1,2888	1,2098	1,1442	1,0887	0,0411	0,9996	0,9631	0,9308	0,9018
340	1,6572	1,5753	1,5037	1,3875	1,2916	1,2231	1,1622	1,1108	1,0667	1,0284	0,9948	0,9649
360		1,6692	1,5813	1,4437	1,3402	1,2589	1,1931	1,1385	1,0923	1,0527	1,0182	0,9879
380		1,7428	1,6338	1,4707	1,3533	1,2639	1,1932	1,1356	1,0876	1,0469	1,0118	0,9812
400		1,8179	1,6801	1,4844	1,3503	1,2517	1,1756	1,1147	1,0647	1,0227	0,9370	0,9561
420		1,9233	1,7425	1,5017	1,3459	1,2455	1,1524	1,0871	1,0344	0,9906	0,9537	0,9221
440		2,0996	1,8488	1,5408	1,3545	1,2276	1,1346	1,0631	1,0061	0,9594	0,9204	0,8872
460		2,4156	2,0393	1,6231	1,3903	1,2398	1,1323	1,0514	0,9878	0,9364	0,8939	0,8579
480		3,0091	2,3793	1,7763	1,4723	1,2845	1,1552	1,0601	0,9867	0,9278	0,8797	0,8394
500		4,2184	2,9927	2,9426	1,6216	1,3771	1,2147	1,0981	1,0096	0,9400	0,8835	0,8366

50% normal fatty aldehyde +50% isofatty aldehyde heat coefficient
($\alpha \cdot 10^3, K^{-1}$)

P,MP _a T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	1,3558	1,2987	1,2485	1,1626	1,0916	1,0318	0,9804	0,9359	0,8867	8620	0,8310	0,8574
320	1,5402	1,4706	1,4087	1,3058	1,2233	1,1554	1,0983	1,0495	1,0872	0,9702	0,9374	0,9081
340	1,6849	1,4971	1,5211	1,3989	1,3044	1,2286	1,1602	1,1198	1,0691	1,0304	0,9965	0,9664
360		1,6881	1,5947	1,4503	1,3429	1,2594	1,1924	1,1368	1,0901	1,0502	1,0156	0,9852
380		1,7607	1,6497	1,4735	1,3520	1,2604	1,1885	1,1302	1,0818	1,0409	1,0058	0,9753
400		1,8379	1,6906	1,4851	1,3465	1,2456	1,1683	1,1068	1,0565	1,0144	0,9787	0,9478
420		1,9505	1,7561	1,5025	1,3414	1,2283	1,14391	1,0780	1,0248	0,9810	0,9440	0,9134
440		2,1423	1,8704	1,5443	1,3510	1,2209	1,1252	1,0539	0,9964	0,9495	0,9103	0,8771
460		2,4889	2,0756	2,6322	1,3904	1,2349	1,1252	1,0430	0,9787	0,9269	0,8841	0,8479
480		3,1481	2,4435	1,7055	1,4772	1,2831	1,1506	1,0535	0,9788	0,9193	0,8707	0,8301
500		4,5122	3,1091	3,0784	1,6353	1,3812	1,2141	1,0945	1,0042	0,9333	0,8759	0,8284

25% normal fatty aldehyde +75 isofatty aldehyde heat index
($\alpha \cdot 10^3, K^{-1}$)

P,MP _a T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	1,3868	1,3280	1,2748	1,1845	1,1104	1,0484	0,9954	0,9496	0,9096	0,8742	0,8426	0,8143
320	1,5707	1,4965	1,4309	1,3229	1,2371	1,1669	1,1082	1,0583	1,0153	0,9777	0,9446	0,9150
340	1,7133	1,6194	1,5388	1,4107	1,3126	1,2346	1,1708	1,1175	1,0721	1,0330	0,9988	0,9686
360		1,7076	1,6085	1,4572	1,3462	1,2605	1,1921	1,1358	1,0887	1,0485	1,0137	0,9834
380		1,7793	1,6561	1,4768	1,3514	1,2576	1,1845	1,1256	1,0768	1,0358	1,0006	0,9701
400		1,8593	1,7022	1,4867	1,3436	1,2405	1,1619	1,0997	1,0491	1,0069	0,9712	0,9404
420		1,9800	1,7714	1,5046	1,3381	1,2224	1,1366	1,0699	1,0165	0,9725	0,9355	0,9038
440		2,1892	1,8944	1,5497	1,3492	1,2157	1,1193	1,0460	0,9879	0,9407	0,9014	0,8681
460		2,5718	2,1172	1,6444	1,3924	1,2322	1,1199	1,0363	0,9712	0,9187	0,8755	0,8392
480		3,3063	2,5162	1,8190	1,4853	1,2844	1,1482	1,0488	0,9728	0,9124	0,8631	0,8221
500		4,8552	3,2419	2,2419	1,6534	1,3889	1,2162	1,0933	1,0009	0,9284	0,8699	0,8216

Calculated values of the difference in heat capacities of N. fatty aldehyde in different pressure and temperature range ($C_p - C_v, C/(kq \cdot k)$)

P,MP _a T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	563,09	546,9	532,1	506,2	484,4	465,8	449,7	435,5	423,0	411,8	401,7	392,7
320	670,7	652,9	636,9	610,2	588,6	570,9	556,1	549,5	532,8	523,5	515,5	508,4
340	728,6	709,2	692,3	665,4	644,9	629,1	616,5	606,5	598,4	591,8	586,5	582,2
360		721,3	703,2	675,9	656,7	642,7	632,5	624,9	619,5	615,6	612,9	611,2
380		705,5	685,2	656,4	637,5	624,8	616,3	610,6	607,1	605,1	604,4	604,6
400		680,1	655,8	623,2	603,2	509,6	532,6	577,8	575,2	574,2	574,5	575,8
420		662,5	680,9	531,0	567,7	553,4	544,5	533,3	536,5	535,4	535,7	536,9
440		669,1	624,5	571,2	541,3	523,1	511,7	504,5	500,2	497,4	491,1	497,5
460		720,4	650,8	573,9	532,5	507,4	491,2	480,4	473,2	468,5	465,6	463,9
480		852,8	730,9	510,2	549,2	512,6	458,6	471,9	460,1	451,5	445,2	440,6
500		1149,8	930,5	637,4	602,3	546,7	510,1	484,4	465,4	451,04	439,9	431,1

Calculated values of the difference in heat capacities of isofatty aldehyde in different pressure and temperature range ($C_p - C_v$, C/(kg·k)

P,MPa T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	563,9	546,3	530,5	503,9	482,4	464,5	449,6	436,8	425,7	416,1	407,5	400,0
320	643,9	624,6	607,9	581,2	560,8	544,8	532,1	521,7	513,2	506,2	500,4	495,6
340	676,9	655,6	638,1	611,6	592,9	579,4	569,4	561,9	556,5	552,5	549,6	547,7
360		650,9	631,9	605,0	587,7	576,2	568,6	563,7	560,7	559,2	558,9	559,5
380		628,5	606,4	577,5	560,2	549,8	543,5	540,1	538,8	538,9	540,1	542,2
400		606,05	578,5	544,5	525,5	514,4	508,2	505,1	504,2	504,7	506,5	509,1
420		599,6	562,1	518,4	494,9	481,4	473,6	469,3	467,5	467,4	468,5	470,6
440		626,4	570,1	508,9	477,1	485,5	447,3	440,4	436,4	434,4	433,9	434,4
460		712,6	618,4	525,4	479,2	452,2	434,9	423,6	410,9	410,9	407,9	405,7
480		913,1	734,1	580,9	509,9	468,7	441,9	423,5	410,3	400,6	393,3	387,9
500		1362,9	968,6	695,5	581,1	516,5	474,7	445,3	423,7	407,1	394,2	383,8

Calculated values of the difference in heat capacities of the binary mixture consisting of 75% N.fatty aldehyde + 25% isofatty aldehyde in different pressure and temperature range. ($C_p - C_v$, C/(kg·k)

P,MPa T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	562,9	546,4	531,3	505,1	483,3	464,8	448,9	435,1	422,8	412,0	402,3	393,6
320	663,4	645,2	628,9	602,1	580,7	563,4	549,1	537,0	526,8	518,1	510,6	504,1
340	714,6	694,7	677,7	650,7	630,7	615,4	603,5	594,1	586,7	530,8	576,1	572,4
360		702,1	683,8	656,6	637,8	624,8	614,9	608,1	603,3	600,0	587,9	596,9
380		684,1	663,4	634,5	616,1	604,02	596,1	591,1	588,2	586,8	586,6	587,4
400		659,0	634,0	601,1	581,5	569,3	561,9	557,6	555,5	554,5	555,7	557,4
420		643,8	610,9	570,2	546,9	532,9	524,5	519,6	517,1	516,4	517,1	518,6
440		654,8	607,7	552,7	522,6	504,5	493,2	486,3	432,2	480,1	479,4	479,9
460		717,7	638,9	558,6	516,4	491,0	474,7	463,9	456,8	452,1	449,1	447,6
480		859,9	726,5	599,0	536,1	488,7	474,2	457,4	445,6	436,6	430,2	425,5
500		1187,4	911,9	692,0	533,1	535,8	498,2	471,9	452,5	437,7	426,3	417,2

Calculated values of the difference in heat capacities of the binary mixture consisting of 50% N.fatty aldehyde + 50% isofatty aldehyde in different pressure and temperature intervals ($C_p - C_v$, C/(kg·k)

P,MPa T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	563,2	546,2	530,8	505,5	482,7	464,4	448,8	435,2	423,3	412,8	403,3	395,2
320	656,7	638,1	621,7	594,8	579,7	556,8	542,9	531,5	521,9	513,7	506,8	500,8
340	701,5	681,1	663,8	637,0	617,4	602,7	591,4	582,7	575,9	570,6	566,6	563,5
360		684,1	665,5	638,4	620,1	607,4	598,5	592,3	588,2	585,6	584,1	583,6
380		664,2	643,1	614,3	596,3	584,8	577,4	573,0	570,7	569,8	570,2	571,5
400		639,8	614,0	580,8	561,4	549,7	542,7	538,8	537,2	537,1	538,2	540,3
420		627,2	592,9	551,3	528,1	514,3	506,1	501,5	499,3	498,9	489,7	501,5
440		643,2	593,2	536,4	505,8	487,7	476,5	469,7	465,7	463,7	463,2	463,7
460		710,2	629,7	545,7	502,3	476,5	460,0	449,2	441,4	437,2	434,2	432,6
480		872,2	725,7	590,6	525,4	486,9	461,9	444,6	432,3	423,3	416,7	411,8
500		1234,9	425,7	690,1	586,7	527,3	488,6	461,5	441,5	426,2	414,4	404,8

A binary mixture consisting of 25% N.fatty aldehyde + 75% isofatty aldehyde in different pressure and temperature range of heat capacity difference calculated prices

$(C_p - C_v, C/(kq \cdot k))$

P,MPa T,k	0,1	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
300	653,7	546,4	530,7	504,2	482,6	464,5	449,1	435,9	424,5	414,4	405,5	397,6
320	650,4	631,4	614,8	587,9	567,3	550,8	537,5	526,6	517,5	509,9	503,5	498,1
340	689,1	668,2	650,8	624,2	605,0	690,9	580,2	572,1	566,0	561,4	557,9	555,5
360		667,3	648,5	621,2	603,6	591,6	583,3	577,8	574,3	572,2	571,4	571,4
380		645,9	624,4	595,5	577,9	566,9	560,1	556,2	554,4	554,1	554,9	556,6
400		622,2	595,6	562,1	542,9	531,5	524,9	521,5	520,2	520,5	521,9	524,3
420		612,6	576,8	534,2	510,9	497,3	489,3	484,9	482,9	432,7	483,7	485,7
440		633,7	580,8	521,9	490,8	472,6	461,4	454,6	450,6	448,7	448,2	448,7
460		710,0	623,1	534,8	490,1	463,7	446,9	435,9	428,5	423,6	429,5	418,7
480		889,6	728,1	584,5	516,6	476,4	451,2	433,4	420,7	311,3	404,4	399,3
500		1293,3	944,5	691,2	582,7	520,9	480,7	452,6	431,8	416,0	403,6	393,1

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